

ARENA Research Unit

Abstract Representations in Neural Architectures

MAX PLANCK INSTITUTE
FOR SOFTWARE SYSTEMS

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Title: Communication and Engagement Report

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Communication and Engagement Plan

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Preamble:

The aim of this Communication and Engagement Plan is to briefly point out the strategy that ARENA Research Unit had followed for its internal communication among projects and team members as well as its external communications and online presence on social media online platforms. It shows the target platforms, target audience, tools, communication strategy and objectives as well as the progress and achievements during the first two years since establishment of this research unit.

- The first version of the ARENA Communication and Engagement Plan was prepared in November 2023 and can be accessed here: www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10219904
- A brief report of the ARENA communication and engagement activities from M1 to M12 can be found in the ARENA First Year Progress Report: www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12743112
- A brief report of the ARENA communication and engagement activities from M12 to M24 can be found in the ARENA Second Year Progress Report: DOI:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17077859>

In the current version of ARENA Communication and Engagement Plan, we have revised the plan based on our experiences over the past 24 months.

Where necessary, we have modified and adjusted the plan to better suit the team's needs and the nature of the activities.

One of the major changes since the initial plan is that the team has decided not to use the X platform anymore. Based on our experience over the last 24 months, we are now focusing mainly on maintaining the ARENA website and keeping it up to date with all the events and activities. Furthermore, most communication is via external and internal mailing lists, as these have a wider reach.

Internal Communication

This section briefly outlines ARENA's strategy for internal communication, focusing on interactions among team members and across projects. It describes the tools used to keep the team connected, informed, and aligned. The main objectives of internal communication are to keep the team connected and updated, track the progress of projects to ensure that deadlines are met, disseminate project outputs among the ARENA team, and collect feedback from the team on tasks, documents, and decisions.

The primary audience for internal communication is the ARENA team members. English is the designated language for all internal communication activities. A variety of communication tools are employed to support these efforts, including online chat platforms such as Discord, emails distributed via the ARENA mailing list, and regular update emails from the project coordinator. For data sharing, platforms like GitHub, Hessianbox, and the Zenodo community are used. Regular online meetings are held, including monthly project meetings, journal club sessions, and meetings dedicated to early career researchers.

External Communication

This section provides an overview of ARENA's objectives for external communication, focusing on strategies to reach a broader audience through targeted online platforms and communication approaches. The primary objectives are to disseminate the scientific activities, outputs, and achievements of ARENA, to communicate scientific events and activities relevant to fields such as neuroscience, cognitive psychology, and computer science, and to foster open scientific discussions.

The targeted audience for external communication includes both national and international scientists, as well as the general public at both national and international levels. English is the primary language used for all external communication. ARENA utilizes several platforms to engage external audiences, including the ARENA website, social networks, blogs, and national and international press outlets.

ARENA's external communication strategy is built on two pillars: branding and networking. The branding strategy includes the consistent use of the ARENA logo and a standard colour template. The networking strategy involves showcasing project profiles on the ARENA website with explicit links to project partners and featuring publications with clear links to team members. Additionally, news pieces and events are posted to the ARENA website.

Specific targets have been defined to guide communication efforts. In the short term (2023), the goal is to provide at least two updates per month on the website, such as news about projects or publications. For the mid-term (2024–2025) and long-term (2026 and beyond), further strategies will be developed and refined. The short-term implementation plan was to review and finalize the communication concept and targets, setting up a website update pipeline with clearly assigned responsibilities, preparing an evaluation report on the short-term targets, and revising the mid-term targets along with developing an appropriate implementation plan.